

Investigating options for future Nordic WLCG Tier-1 operations

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1. SURVEYS APPROACH	5
2. BACKGROUND	6
3. CURRENT NDGF-T1 PERFORMANCE RESULTS	9
4. CURRENT NDGF-T1 COSTS ASSESSMENT (2015)	21
5. SINGLE-SITE NDGF-T1: COSTS MODEL	35
6. INTERMEDIATE COSTS MODELS FOR THE NDGF-T1	41
7. EVALUATION OF THE NON-MONETARY ASPECTS	45
8. RISKS ASSESSMENT	46
9. RECOMMENDATIONS	48
10. CONCLUSIONS	49
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	50
REFERENCES	51

Executive Summary

This report presents the results of a cost-efficiency study for the current configuration, and of other possible configurations, of the Nordic WLCG Tier-1 (NDGF-T1), as well as some guidelines to improve its computing operations. Evaluation of different options for deployment and operations, in particular if a centralized mode improves costs compared to the current distributed setup across four countries is presented. The report estimates the effects of the different modes of operations, listing the advantages and disadvantages together with the estimated costs, including a risk assessment approach for transitions and an evaluation of the non-monetary aspects for the different modes of operation that are proposed. Along the document, additional suggestions for efficiency improvements are provided, no matter what decision is made with regards to the NDGF-T1 re-organization, since the current mode of operations would be in place for several years in either case.

This project involved engagement with a multitude of stakeholders, from core-computing teams of the ATLAS and ALICE collaborations up to relevant actors in Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden, mainly Principal Investigators (P.I.s) of national R&D projects and computing service providers offering resources to the NDGF-T1, namely NBI, CSC, UiB, UiO, HPC2N, and NSC HPC sites. Physical meetings occurred during the execution of the project, from conferences and some visits to the HPC sites (HPC2N, and NBI), but the main element to collect the relevant information as seed for this cost-efficiency alternatives study came from dedicated surveys circulated to all of the stakeholders, and many consecutive follow-ups. All this feedback was collected in the period from October 2015 to April 2016.

The bulk information about the Tier-1 budget structures for each site and country has been gathered from the sites and P.Is. Given the nature of the HPC sites, some of the Tier-1 costs were difficult to be provided, such as the electricity costs of the HPC clusters or the costs of shared services for the Tier-1 (like tape systems). This report provides reasonable estimations for all of these costs.

The current derived cost for the distributed NDGF-T1 is ~ 3 M€/year. Around $\sim 44\%$ of the Tier-1 funding comes from national R&D programs and Infrastructure calls, and $\sim 33\%$ from NeIC. The current Tier-1 distributed configuration benefits from the Tier-1 resources being co-located in large HPC sites, as well as from local personnel contributing to Tier-1 Operations activities. The HPC sites contribute with $\sim 15\%$ of the Tier-1 personnel, and with most of the electricity and infrastructure costs. These in-kind contributions cover $\sim 23\%$ of the Tier-1 costs. The total amount for in-kind contributions from the HPC sites is estimated to be ~ 0.7 M€/year. It is worth mentioning that around half of the Tier-1 budget is spent in personnel.

The costs for deploying the NDGF-T1 in a single site have been addressed. As expected, this configuration provides the most cost-effective Tier-1 scenario. The main savings are related to personnel needs, reduced network costs, since the network costs to interconnect sites are not present, and a reduction on the infrastructure (including a reduction on tape libraries) and generic Tier-1 services costs. The cost for this configuration is estimated in ~ 2.3 M€/year. As compared to the current NDGF-T1 configuration, this scenario provides a reduction of the Tier-1 budget by ~ 0.7 M€/year. This reduction is similar to the current in-kind contributions from the HPC sites that conform the distributed NDGF-T1.

Additional (intermediate) scenarios have been considered, such as reducing the number of HPC sites per country, deploying the Tier-1 in a single-site in the Nordics,

with hardware tendered and purchased by each of the current participating sites, or transferring all of the Tier-1 Operations effort to the central Tier-1 NeIC Operations team. The savings in these scenarios are -0.4 M€/year, -0.3 M€/year, and a marginal value of -125 k€/year, respectively.

This study shows that the current in-kind contributions from the HPC sites are comparable to the savings obtained by deploying the NDGF-T1 in a single location. Additionally, there are sociological aspects to consider. The degree of involvement from the countries might decrease if the resources are not operated locally. There is the risk that the skilled distributed personnel is lost, and this would have a negative impact in the future NDGF-T1 activities, since Tier-1 involvement is seen as important and strategic from the sites perspective. This said, there could be political difficulties in locating the entire NDGF-T1 at one location since it would involve sending money across borders. A possible alternative NDGF-T1 architecture with reduced number of sites in each country provides a cost-effective solution, preserving the skilled distributed knowledge and competences. This model has good resiliency built in.

Important innovations and scientific-technological developments have originated from WLCG computing related activities. Other fields of science have benefited from the transfer of knowledge of LHC data processing and distributed computing techniques. Typically, the Tier-1s act as drivers in these activities. Despite its success and effectiveness, the WLCG system needs some tuning during the next years, and will need to reinvent itself to face the extraordinary challenges ahead during the HL-LHC era. It is therefore necessary to join all of the available forces for a new stage of an ambitious R&D programme to meet these new challenges. The development efforts made in the Nordic countries, mainly in ARC and dCache services, have a positive impact in WLCG. Future R&D activities in WLCG focus in storage federations, and NDGF-T1 development team can play an important role in these activities.

This report comes from a request by the NeIC Board, and it is intended to be input to the NeIC's planning for the future configuration of the Nordic Tier-1 collaboration.

1. Surveys approach

This study has implied engagement of a multitude of stakeholders, from core-computing teams of the ALICE and ATLAS collaborations up to relevant actors in Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden, mainly Principal Investigators (P.Is) of national LHC R&D projects and computing service providers offering services to the NDGF-T1, namely NBI, CSC, UiB, UiO, HPC2N, and NSC.

Dedicated surveys were built to collect all of the relevant feedback for the project. Three types of surveys were used to collect information from the ALICE and ATLAS collaborations (~30 questions), the country P.Is (~20 questions), and the HPC sites (~50 questions). All of this information was collected in the period from October 2015 to April 2016.

By means of these surveys, the ALICE and ATLAS collaborations feedback on resources exploitation and computing operations for the current NDGF-T1 configuration was collected. From the dedicated surveys to P.Is and HPC sites, the most sensitive information was gathered, such as detailed information on the Tier-1 budget structures, the services provided to the Tier-1 and estimations of the Tier-1 running costs. Some of the costs were difficult to calculate, such as the electricity costs of the clusters or the costs of shared services for the Tier-1 (like tape systems). Many technical areas were addressed, in order to make an accurate estimation of these costs along this study. The surveys addressed non-monetary aspects and how important is the Tier-1 participation from both the sites and the regions perspective.

Figure 1 shows the completeness levels for the surveys circulated, from the first answers up to the final follow-up. The average level of completeness was very high, and this was much appreciated. The level of responsiveness and details in the responses has been very satisfactory.

Figure 1: Level of completeness for the surveys that were circulated to all the relevant stakeholders for this project.

2. Background

The LHC [1], at the European Laboratory for Particle Physics (CERN [2], Switzerland), started operating in November 2009 and it has generated up to date around 400 Petabytes of raw, simulated and processed data, from all of its detectors. To analyse the unprecedented rate of PB of data per year, a Grid-based computer network infrastructure was built, the largest scientific distributed computing infrastructure in the world, adding up the computing resources of more than 170 centers in 34 countries: the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG [3]). In the WLCG, the computing centers are functionally classified in Tiers. Eleven of these centers are the so-called Tier-1s, receiving a copy of the raw data in real time from the Tier-0 at CERN, and in charge of massive data processing, storage and distribution.

The Nordic countries contribute to the WLCG with one Tier-1 center and several Tier-2 centers, supporting the ALICE, ATLAS and CMS collaborations. The NDFG-T1 is a Tier-1 center with distributed resources in 6 HPC sites that are located in Denmark (NBI), Finland (CSC), Norway (UiB, UiO) and Sweden (HPC2N, NSC). NDGF-T1 provides services to two of the LHC experiments, ALICE and ATLAS, targeting for 9% and 6% of the total Tier-1 resources, respectively.

The country shares for the deployed ALICE and ATLAS Tier-1 resources are based on the relative percentage of authors who participate in these international collaborations. Table 1 shows the relative percentage of ALICE and ATLAS authors in the Nordic countries, for the years 2013, 2014 and 2015. Since these contributions are very stable, the average relative percentage of authors per country is as well shown. Norway and Sweden have strong presence in ALICE and ATLAS, respectively. Table 2 shows which experiments are supported at the different HPC sites.

	2013		2014		2015		Average	
	ALICE	ATLAS	ALICE	ATLAS	ALICE	ATLAS	ALICE	ATLAS
DK	18%	21%	17%	22%	18%	22%	18%	22%
FI	20%	-	19%	-	18%	-	19%	-
NO	54%	31%	56%	29%	57%	27%	56%	29%
SE	8%	47%	8%	49%	7%	51%	8%	49%

Table 1: Relative percentage (%) of ALICE and ATLAS authors in Denmark (DK), Finland (FI), Norway (NO), and Sweden (SE), in the period from 2013 to 2015.

Country	HPC center	ALICE	ATLAS
Denmark	NBI		
Finland	CSC		
Norway	UiO		
	UiB		
Sweden	NSC		
	HPC2N		

Table 2: Availability of resources for ALICE and ATLAS at the HPC sites that conform the NDGF-T1.

The WLCG collaboration is governed by a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU [4]) signed between CERN and the institutions hosting Tier-1 and Tier-2 centers, represented by their Funding Agencies. The WLCG MoU defines the service levels to be provided by these centers and determines the resources to be provided by each

center, by means of a Computing Resources Review Board (C-RRB), which meets twice per year, in spring and autumn [5]. The C-RRB oversees and officially approves both the requested resources by the LHC experiments. The NDGF-T1 sets as a target providing 9% and 6% of the total Tier-1 resources for ALICE and ATLAS, respectively. The NDGF-T1 resources are provided by HPC centers that do not step up yearly to accommodate to these Tier-1 needs, since the resources are (typically) deployed once and then operated for several years. The Tier-1 needs are discussed year by year with the HPC sites and the systems are adjusted to deliver the resources accordingly to the country shares. This translates to a delivery of resources that does not exactly match the target, as can be seen in **Figure 2**. Sometimes the deviations from the targets translate in deficits or surpluses in the NDGF-T1 pledges to WLCG [6], which might be related to lack of funds to meet the targets or to try to maximize the use of available installed resources for the NDGF-T1 at the HPC centers, respectively.

Figure 2: Percentage of ALICE and ATLAS resources deployed at the NDGF-T1 (w.r.t. the experiments requests), in comparison to the NDGF-T1 targets, in the period from 2013 to 2015.

Figure 3: ALICE and ATLAS NDGF-T1 deployed CPU, Disk and Tape resources (pledged to WLCG) for the years 2013, 2014 and 2015.

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the NDGF-T1 pledges for ALICE and ATLAS experiments. In December 2014, the ATLAS resources from the Norway UNINETT SIGMA Tier-2 were decommissioned and integrated into the NDGF-T1. Around 3.2

kHSo6 [7] and 0.5 PB, for CPU and Disk resources, were transferred to the Tier-1. As requested by ALICE, there was a decrease of the Tape requests for the years 2014 and 2015 at the Tier-1s. The relative percentage of deployed CPU, Disk and Tape resources in December 2015 per Country and HPC site is shown in **Table 3**.

Country	HPC center	CPU		Disk		Tape	
Denmark	NBI	19%		22%		30%	
Finland	CSC	7%		3%		-	
Norway	UiO	15%	32%	21%	43%	16%	22%
	UiB	17%		22%		6%	
Sweden	NSC	25%	42%	19%	32%	19%	48%
	HPC2N	17%		13%		29%	

Table 3: Relative percentage of deployed NDGF-T1 CPU, Disk and Tape resources in each country and HPC site, by December 2015.

The NDGF-T1 external connectivity is partly based on a layer 2 private network, the so-called LHC Optical Private Network (LHCOPN) [8], which interconnects the Tier-1 with CERN and the rest of the Tier-1s in WLCG. The NDGF-T1 connects, via NORDUnet, to the LHCOPN with one 10 Gbps link to CERN via GÉANT, and one backup 10 Gbps link to CERN via Hamburg/Amsterdam, as shown in Figure 4. The different HPC sites use NORDUnet NRENs to interconnect using 10 Gbps links. An additional 10 Gbps link interconnects NDGF-T1 and Slovenia IJS computing center.

Figure 4: LHCOPN network map, showing primary and backup links.

3. Current NDGF-T1 performance results

One of the main characteristics of Tier-1 centres is that, beyond providing a very large storage and computing capacity, they must do so through services that need to be extremely reliable. These are among the cornerstones of the Tier-1 responsibilities. The delivery of pledged capacity, the resources usage, and a collection of handful performance metrics, including the services quality and stability, are closely tracked and monitored by the WLCG organization and the LHC experiments. This section focuses on all of the available performance metrics of the NDGF-T1 for the last five years, as well as comparisons to other Tier-1 centers.

Resource provisioning and usage

Figure 5, Figure 6, and Figure 7 show the CPU, Disk and Tape resource provisioning in the NDGF-T1, respectively, compared to the overall Tier-1 pledge for each of the resources, and the resource utilization from ALICE and ATLAS. This information is reported from the NDGF-T1 to WLCG Office in a monthly basis [9]. As stated in the previous section, the NDGF-T1 pledges are set every yearly based on pre-established targets, and modelled by the available resources, however the installed capacities reported to WLCG slightly differ from the pledges.

Historically, it has been difficult for the NDGF-T1 central Operations team to report about the correct installed resource capacities to WLCG. The installed capacities can include additional resources that are used by the Tier-1, which are not pledged to WLCG, such as part of the Slovenia IJS Disk resources that are used by the Tier-1, or the usage of additional CPU resources in big HPC sites where the Tier-1 is embedded. On the other hand, the NDGF-T1 central Operations team very well monitors the usage of the resources.

Figure 5: Accounting of the CPU capacity of NDGF-T1, since Jan. 2010. Installed capacity (black) is compared to the capacity pledged according to the WLCG MoU (purple). Used resources by the LHC experiments are as well shown.

Figure 6: Accounting of the Disk capacity of NDGF-T1, since Jan. 2010. Installed capacity (black) is compared to the capacity pledged according to the WLCG MoU (purple). Used resources by the LHC experiments are as well shown.

Figure 7: Accounting of the Tape capacity of NDGF-T1, since Jan. 2010. Installed capacity (black) is compared to the capacity pledged according to the WLCG MoU (purple). Used resources by the LHC experiments are as well shown.

Resource usage in comparison to other Tier-1s

Since all of the Tier-1s in WLCG report monthly about their resource usage, it is very convenient to compare the NDGF-T1 resource usages to those observed at other Tier-1 centers. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the CPU, Disk and Tape utilization as compared to the pledge (indeed, the ratio used/pledged) for both ALICE and ATLAS and the average utilization trends observed at the Tier-1s, since January 2010.

For ALICE, the CPU utilization at the NDGF-T1 has been continuously increasing, from an average utilization ratio of 50% in 2010 up to a ratio of ~150% in 2015. The same trend is observed at the rest of Tier-1s, which indicates that ALICE has been increasing their activities at the Tier-1 sites. It is worth mentioning that ALICE can pressure sites to get, at least +50% additional CPU usage with respect to the pledged resources. This is mainly driven by the fact that ALICE runs in Tier-1s that serve

more than one LHC experiment, hence it can opportunistically access to unused resources at these sites. Concerning the Disk resources, it is worth mentioning that ALICE is constantly using $\sim 50\%$ of the pledged resources in NDGF-T1, a general trend observed at all of the Tier-1s. The Tape resources deployed in the NDGF-T1 have been underused until recently, when the ALICE experiment has started accumulating data from the LHC Run2. The Heavy Ion runs took place at the end of 2015 and data replication to Tier-1s takes ~ 2 months after the end of data taking. Almost all of the available tapes at the Tier-1s were utilized by February 2016.

Figure 8: ALICE used CPU, Disk and Tape resources at the NDGF-T1, as compared to the ALICE NDGF-T1 pledges, since Jan. 2010. The average of used/pledged resources at the ALICE Tier-1s is shown for comparisons.

For ATLAS, almost all of the available CPU at the NDGF-T1 is normally used, a typical trend which is observed at the ATLAS Tier-1s. ATLAS can typically exploit additional resources at the Tier-1 sites, reaching +50-100% above the pledges. In the recent years, NDGF-T1 has properly delivered to ATLAS, in agreement with the NDGF-T1 pledges. The NDGF-T1 typically provides more disk than the pledge to ATLAS. The additional disk contribution from Slovenia IJS center to the NDGF-T1, and the deployment of more disk than expected due to good tenders, explains the situation. The tape is efficiently used by ATLAS at the NDGF-T1. The usage pattern seen at the NDGF-T1 matches perfectly the trend observed at the ATLAS Tier-1s.

Figure 9: ATLAS used CPU, Disk and Tape resources at the NDGF-T1, as compared to the ATLAS NGDF-T1 pledges, since Jan. 2010. The average of used/pledged resources at the ATLAS Tier-1s is shown for comparisons.

Network connectivity

The primary LHCOPN link that connects the NDGF-T1 with CERN and the rest of Tier-1s has been running with a bandwidth of 10 Gbps. Many Tier-1s upgraded their LHCOPN connectivity during the LHC shutdown period (2013-2014), up to 20 Gbps, or even 100 Gbps. Figure 10 shows the last year traffic in the NDGF-T1 LHCOPN link. Since saturation periods have recently been seen, the NDGF-T1 has undergone a recent network revision, to include an additional 10 Gbps LHCONE link, to interconnect to the LHC Tier-2s, and improving its General IP connection, by means of an additional 10 Gbps link [10]. According to the last year monitoring view [11] provided by CERN, the NDGF-T1 has transferred a volume of 8.6 PB of data, accounting for ~4% of the total traffic handled by the LHCOPN, as seen in Figure 11.

The main NDGF-T1 router is placed in Denmark. Since Sweden and Norway host ~75% of the NDGF-T1 data, it is seen that the 10 Gbps links which interconnect the sites in these countries to the central router might need a further revision (i.e. a bandwidth upgrade).

Figure 10: LHCOPN traffic in/out to the NDGF-T1, from May 2015 to May 2016.

Figure 11: 1-year period of LHCOPN traffic in/out at the LHC Tier-1s, from May 2015 to May 2016. NDGF-T1 contributes 3.8% of the total LHCOPN traffic.

NDGF-T1 site reliability

All of the critical services quality and stability are closely tracked by monitoring two metrics provided by the SAM monitoring framework: the so-called *availability* and *reliability* metrics [12]. These are built from dozens of sensors, for each of the experiments, which hourly probe the entire site Grid services, ensuring peer pressure and guaranteeing that the reliability of WLCG service keeps improving. The MoU sets a yearly average target of 97% for the *reliability* metric at the Tier-1 centers.

Until 2014, generic tests ('ops' tests) were used to compare the *reliabilities* at the sites towards the targets. Since 2014, the more detailed experiments SAM frameworks are used. The recent years SAM *reliability* Tier-1 rankings for both the 'ops' and ATLAS SAM frameworks are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13, respectively. The measured reliabilities at the NDGF-T1 consistently meet the MoU targets, with the exception of the year 2015, where the measured ATLAS reliability was of 96.7%. Besides that, the NDGF-T1 is a stable site towards WLCG.

ALICE does not have a functional SAM framework established for the NDGF-T1. The ALICE jobs at the NDGF-T1 HPC sites are submitted from dedicated local machines (VOBOXES) to the internal site computing elements (ARC-CEs). These ARC-CEs are typically not open for external job submissions, hence the centralized SAM tests cannot be remotely sent to the NDGF-T1. Additionally, ALICE remotely access files using the *XRootD* protocol [13], and the current SAM framework does not allow to test the *XRootD* storage elements deployed at the sites. ALICE is currently exploring several solutions to integrate NDGF-T1 in their SAM framework.

Figure 12: 'ops' reliability ranking plots for the Tier-0 and Tier-1 sites, in the period from 2010 to 2015.

Figure 13: ATLAS *reliability* ranking plots for the Tier-0 and Tier-1 sites, for the years 2014 and 2015.

CPU efficiency of the executed jobs

CPU Efficiency measured as the ratio between the CPU time and the total execution time (walltime) for the executed jobs in a site is an important metric to be tracked. The CPU time relates to the time the CPU spends its computing capacities on a specific task whereas the walltime describes the time needed to execute the computing task. Values below 100% often arise from situations where the CPU is waiting for data, e.g. data coming from the local or remote storages. Real life situations make all of the jobs to be under 100%, and in particular I/O intensive jobs display lower CPU efficiencies. Since the CPU efficiency of the jobs can be affected by changes on experiment analysis software, or by malfunctioning or bad performing configurations of the site storage systems, it is advisable to compare the measured CPU efficiency at the NDGF-T1 with other Tier-1 centers, since the activities run at the Tier-1s are very similar elsewhere.

Figure 14 shows the ALICE CPU efficiency, in a 5-year period. There is a significant difference of NDGF-T1 values when compared to the average CPU efficiency of ALICE jobs run at the Tier-1 centers. Since the data is distributed in all of the HPC sites that conform the NDGF-T1, but presented to the ALICE collaboration as a single storage element (SE), the jobs that run in a given site read most of the data from disk pools that are very distant. The effect seen here is dominated by the latency to read data from remote sites. There is an on-going discussion with the NDGF storage experts on how to improve the CPU/Wall time ratio for the ALICE jobs. This is two pronged: the SE to provide location information and for the ALICE jobs to be less-dependent on 'closeness' of data (*caching* or *read-ahead* techniques). As seen in the previous section, the CPU resources overprovisioning for ALICE in the NDGF-T1 compensate for the lower efficiency, thus this optimization process should be sufficient to bring the system to the level offered by the other Tier-1 centers.

Some periods with low CPU Efficiency for ATLAS jobs in NDGF-T1 are seen, when compared to other Tiers-1, as shown in Figure 15. The HPC sites that support ATLAS are using *data caches* on shared file systems to serve the ATLAS input files (ARC caches). In some cases, the I/O stress on these file systems is too high, and the system is not capable to handle the load. Some problematic caches, affecting the overall CPU efficiency of the NDGF-T1, dominate the effect that is seen here. Since the CPU resources are growing (i.e. the number of running jobs) this effect naturally worsens.

In light of these results, some sites have improved their caches, by expanding them, or by deploying better performing hardware with more IOPS. It is worth mentioning that the most I/O intensive ATLAS campaigns (e.g. *digi-reco*) should yield low CPU efficiencies elsewhere.

Figure 14: ALICE CPU efficiency at the NDGF-T1, as compared to the average values from all of the ALICE Tier-1s, since Jan. 2010.

Figure 15: ATLAS CPU efficiency at the NDGF-T1, as compared to the average values from all of the ATLAS Tier-1s, since Jan. 2010

Job completion Efficiencies

The successful and failed jobs that have run at a site are good indicators of the job qualities, i.e. how well a site delivers CPU to the experiments. The job completion efficiency can be measured as the ratio of the success jobs over the total jobs handled by a site. Figure 16 shows the comparison of the job completion efficiency for ATLAS jobs at the NDGF-T1, in comparison to the average value seen at the ATLAS Tier-1s. The trend for NDGF-T1 is very similar to the average observed at the ATLAS Tier-1s, except for the periods in which some of the distributed NDGF-T1 ARC caches were under-performing.

ALICE central system typically retries up to 3 times for failed jobs. In general, ~93% of the jobs success at first execution, ~98% after one retry and another ~1% after 2 retries. The NDGF-T1 failure rate is comparable to other Tier-1 sites. For a failing job due to data access problems, a second available replica is accessed, which is by design not at NDGF-T1. This (unavailability of part of a SE or entire SE) is the reason that the ALICE jobs have about ~5% remote (WAN) access, in general.

Figure 16: ATLAS Job completion efficiency at the NDGF-T1, as compared to the average values from all of the ATLAS Tier-1s, since Jan. 2010

Response to operational issues

GGUS (Global Grid User Support) [14] is the primary channel to request for support when using the Grid. This ticketing system is used by the experiments to notify the WLCG sites in case of troubles. The tickets are classified according to the severity of the problem observed. The categories are: less urgent, urgent, very urgent, and top priority. Figure 17 shows the number of tickets sent to all WLCG Tier-1 centers, since 2013. Typically, NDGF-T1 does not get more tickets than other Tier-1s. In particular, it has received less “top priority” tickets than the rest of the Tier-1 centers. Tickets that are sent to the NDGF-T1 are acknowledged in less than half an hour, and they are typically resolved in less than one day and a half. These are typical reaction and solution times that are seen at other Tier-1 centers.

Figure 17: GGUS tickets sent to Tier-1 sites, ordered by severity, since 2013.

Site downtimes

NDGF-T1 reports the (minimal) downtimes affecting the site, or any of the HPC sites, well in advance through GOCDB [15], providing very detailed information for all of the affected services. This is well appreciated by the ALICE and ATLAS experiments.

ALICE and ATLAS collaboration feedback

In general, the resources exploitation at NDGF-T1 is stable and satisfactory, from the ALICE and ATLAS computing operations point of view. The NDGF-T1 liaisons regularly participate in the Operations meetings, and the NDGF-T1 administrators make sure that all of the HPC sites are operational and performing according to the required Quality of Service (QoS). NDGF-T1 has a good record of proactive measures to prevent security incidents, and complies quickly and properly with all the needed critical security updates. No security incidents have been observed so far.

For ALICE, since each HPC site at the NDGF-T1 manages their internal job submissions, at any given time most of the NDGF-T1 computing capacity is available, even when one site has a downtime. Most of the data is available, provided that the central *dCache* services are available. Otherwise, data can be remotely accessed from any other Tier-1. The access to tape system is properly controlled by ALICE, and any downtime or unavailability of any of the data on tape in the NDGF-T1 does not negatively impact ALICE computing operations. For technical reasons SAM does not yet test the NDGF-T1, but like all ALICE sites, the individual HPC centers that conform the NDGF-T1 are monitored by MonALISA [16] for services status and performance. ALICE collaboration acknowledges the proactive involvement of personnel from NDGF-T1 in R&D activities, such as integration of Cloud paradigms into AliEn [17].

ATLAS operates the NDGF-T1 in a different way, not by the fact that the resources are distributed, just because the NDGF-T1 is managed through the ARC Control Tower [18], as well as other NorduGrid Tier-2s. The deployed ARC-CEs at the HPC sites that conform the NDGF-T1 use failover, i.e. if the input files cannot be read from any of the NDGF-T1 sites, they are downloaded to the ARC caches from other locations, if available. Jobs with unique input on NDGF-T1 can wait on ARC-CE until the SE is up again, in case of problems with accessing data that is only present in the NDGF-T1. Other jobs can fill the NDGF-T1 sites in the meantime. As contrary to WLCG, ATLAS is not using the SAM tests as a real measure of good stability of the sites. The *HammerCloud* tests [19] are the ones checked more often, and in this respect NDGF-T1 performance is similar to the ones seen at other Tier-1s.

The ALICE and ATLAS collaborations appreciate the support by both the NDGF-T1 *dCache* and ARC teams, which has been excellent so far.

Findings and recommendations

Finding #3.1: Since 2015, the resource provisioning at the sites should be done without taking into account efficiency factors (i.e. application of efficiency corrections for the CPU, Disk and Tape pledges). Recommendation: this should be clarified to all of the HPC sites that conform the NDGF-T1, since it is not widely acknowledged.

Finding #3.2: WLCG accounting irregularities have been observed at the NDGF-T1, in particular with respect to the installed CPU, Disk and Tape resources. Recommendation: since this high-level accounting in WLCG is commonly shown to Funding Agencies, it is recommended to establish a mechanism to properly report on installed capacities. For CPU resources, most of the HPC centers have limited resources for the NDGF-T1, others allow using more resources, if available. This can add +10% of CPU at these sites, and this can be taken as a reference to report on installed CPU. For Disk, the additional resources added by the Slovenia IJS Tier-2 should be consistently reported. The installed tape capacity requires information from local sites. A mechanism to (internally) monitor the deployed and used capacities should be established, in order to provide a consistent view to WLCG.

Finding #3.3: NO-NORGRID-T2 resources were added to the NDGF-T1 in December 2014. These resources were reported to WLCG both at NO-NORGRID-T2 and the NDGF-T1 for the nominal WLCG 2014 year. The actual resources were deployed in exact same place as were the NDGF-T1, but from the accounting point of view these resources were doubled counted in WLCG.

Finding #3.4: There is more installed disk than needed in the NDGF-T1, mostly thanks to the contributions from Slovenia IJS Tier-2. To properly access this data (~1 PB), a dedicate 10 Gbps connection is set from NDGF-T1 to the Slovenia IJS Tier-2 center. Recommendation: the cost of this additional link is ~25 k€/year, which is typically the cost of deploying ~1 PB disk for a 4 years lifetime. It is recommended to integrate Slovenia IJS Tier-2 in the general LHCONE network from NDGF-T1 to the WLCG Tier-2 centers, and reduce this network cost.

Finding #3.5: the SAM tests *reliabilities* are critical metrics in WLCG. In the year 2015, the NDGF-T1 ATLAS site reliability was below the WLCG threshold (set to 97%). Recommendation: monitor closely the reliability of the NDGF-T1 towards the experiments, and ask for monthly corrections in case of false reliabilities reported, i.e. if the low reliabilities are not related to the NDGF-T1, but rather related to the experiment SAM framework. These metrics are show to Funding Agencies, since good reliabilities are required, according to the MoU.

Finding #3.6: ALICE does not have a functional SAM framework established for the NDGF-T1. Recommendation: work in close contact with ALICE and the HPC sites to enable this monitoring in the NDGF-T1 as soon as possible, since the MoU foresees monitoring this metric for the Tier-1 centers.

Finding #3.7: perfSONAR-PS [20] is a toolkit to detect network performance issues. NORDUnet hosts a central perfSONAR-PS service, together with the NDGF-T1 dCache central nodes. Hence, this service is not useful to detect network problems in the NDGF-T1, since the resources are distributed among several sites. Recommendation: Evaluate enabling independent instances of perfSONAR-PS at all of the HPC centers that conform the NDGF-T1.

Finding #3.8: Low CPU/Wall time ratios observed for the ALICE jobs running in the NDGF-T1. Recommendation: work in close contact with ALICE and the NDGF-T1

storage experts to develop mechanisms to improve the efficiency, by means of reading closer data (low latency), or deploying caching techniques.

Finding #3.9: Low CPU/Wall time ratios observed for the ATLAS I/O intensive jobs. Recommendation: monitor closely the quality of the storages deployed as ARC caches in the sites, and eventually running scalability checks to detect any possible bottleneck.

Finding #3.10: There is no 24x7 support provided in the NDGF-T1. Since the NDGF-T1 is deployed in 6 HPC centers, the non-availability of a center simply impacts in a degradation of a given Tier-1 service. Recommendation: both ALICE and ATLAS did not observe particular issues. This meets the requirements set by the WLCG MoU, however, if the number of HPC centers supporting the NDGF-T1 decrease, this might need a revision.

Finding #3.11: 10 Gbps connections from some countries to the central NORDUnet router is not seen as enough. Recommendation: this can impact Norway and Sweden, since most of the Tier-1 resources are deployed in these countries. Monitor closely the network usage to react upon eventual network upgrades.

Finding #3.12: SLAs for the Tier-1 services deployed at the sites are not formally established. Recommendation: elaboration of SLAs, or expectations for the deployed services, so the different HPC sites know on the criticalities of the different services they operate, and procedures for efficient operation of the services.

Finding #3.13: Resources tracking (deployment dates, capacities, operational issues, warranty constrains, retirement dates) cost efforts for the central NDGF-T1 team. Recommendation: deploying a lightweight open-source Data Center Infrastructure Management tool, such as *openDCIM* [21], to keep track the NDGF-T1 inventory, with the Central Operations team and site administrators as responsible for maintaining it up-to-date.

Finding #3.14: site administrators and NDGF-T1 Central Operations team communicate often and fluently, in particular very efficiently through a chat service (neic.slack.com), and through many get together sessions along the year. This keeps a very committed team, spreading the expertise around. Recommendation: the CPU usage at the sites is compared weekly, and targets at the sites are set, to allow for applications of corrections on the batch system, if the sites can do it. Since the pledges are compared weekly, this way of overviewing the used of resources should take more than one week time-window, to allow for better corrections.

Finding #3.15: The NDGF-T1 Operations meetings are well established, but there is lack of NDGF-T1 management meetings. Recommendation: these meetings should be established, at least once every 2 months, were the different HPC sites and the Tier-1 management strategically discuss about future needs and plans.

4. Current NDGF-T1 costs assessment (2015)

Four countries deploy resources for the NDGF-T1. The way in which the funds are obtained, and spent, depends on different models that are present in these countries. Typically, most of the budget comes from national R&D programs, and it is complemented by funds from the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC [22]), an organisation, funded by all of the Nordic countries, that facilitates the development and operation of high-quality e-Infrastructure solutions in areas of joint Nordic interest. NeIC, tightly coupled to the Tier-1 since its creation, helps the Nordic Tier-1 by funding technical experts from academic high-performance computing centres across the Nordic countries, and additional funding for common Tier-1 services. Since the HPC sites that conform the NDGF-T1 provide services to other projects, and in particular as they are deployed in Universities, there are many in-kind contributions to the NDGF-T1. In-kind contributions from National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) in the Nordic countries are as well present.

This funding is spent to deploy the NDGF-T1 resources and central services, part of the Tier-1 running costs, to cover most of the needed personnel, and to finance part of the needed network connectivity for the NDGF-T1 and some of the network expenses at the HPC centers. This section provides an estimation of the total costs for running the NDGF-T1, with costs breakdown per categories and countries, for a better understanding of the NDGF-T1 funding structure. Most of this information has been obtained from the stakeholders, and some of the (unavailable) data has been estimated.

Structure and available funds for the NDGF-T1

The Tier-1 hardware purchases are typically funded by public grants. These computing needs are included as part of global LHC projects that are submitted to calls from national R&D programs. These projects include funding requests for LHC Physics, detector upgrades and computing resources for Tier-1 and Tier-2 sites, including personnel needs. Projects are typically granted for periods of three to four years. Additional computing funds have been obtained by dedicated infrastructure grants, in some of the countries. Investments are typically done once during the execution time of the projects. Since these budgets are subject to reorganizations in the funding schemes, all of the P.Is at the countries have plans to submit new projects to all of the available calls, to maximize the budget for the Tier-1 resources.

Denmark: The Tier-1 resources are deployed in the HPC facilities at the Niels Bohr Institute (NBI) [23], located at the faculty of Sciences at the University of Copenhagen. This HPC facility is used by many different groups, and the Tier-1 resources account for ~10% of the deployed resources in the site. Funding for Tier-1 is supplied by public grants, and typically covers ~35% of the total Tier-1 costs at the site. This budget is spent in hardware purchases, which is then operated by NBI personnel (mostly paid by NeIC). The typical yearly budget from national R&D public grants is ~1 MDKK/year, and the in-kind contributions from the NBI site are comparable. The network costs are in-kind contributed by the NREN/site. The Tier-1 future needs are included in the Danish Roadmap for Research Infrastructures document [24], which defines the Danish vision and strategic objectives for the research infrastructures in the coming five years.

Finland: Helsinki Institute of Physics (HIP) [25] asks for public grants to fund the WLCG activities. Last application was sent to the Finnish Grid and Cloud

Infrastructure program in 2014. The resources are integrated and operated at CSC [26], a major IT provider for Universities and research centers in Finland. Since mid-2015, the WLCG resources were deployed in the *Jade* cluster, a CPU cluster that was used 1/3 for the ALICE Tier-1 and 2/3 for the CMS Tier-2. As of today, all of these CPU resources have been migrated to *cPouta* [27], a new flexible HPC center provisioned from the *Taito* super cluster, which provides an Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). This new data center has been deployed in Kajaani. Since then, the exploitation of these resources is free of costs for academic users, including the Finish Tier-1 and Tier-2 CPU needs. However, the WLCG disk resources are located in CSC, and this seems to be the scenario for the next years. The Ministry of Culture and Education funded these WLCG activities with ~800k€/year for 2008-2010 and afterwards the WLCG activities has been fitted into the HIP base budget. For the years 2014 and 2015, CSC charged HIP with 240 k€ and 229 k€ for the operation of the deployed WLCG resources at CSC, respectively; HIP invested in 2015 ~100 k€ in Tier-1 disk (~700 TB), which will be operated for the next 4 years. In this new scenario, HIP applies for Tier-1 CPU-cycles in *cPouta*, and the fraction of operational support previously provided by CSC should be then covered by funds coming from public grants. This new scenario has de-inflated the budget from public grants for the Tier-1 in Finland by roughly ~25%. This budget, of ~85 k€/year, covers ~25% of the total Tier-1 expenses in Finland. The NREN/site covers the WAN network costs.

Norway: two HPC centers provide support for Tier-1 activities. These centers are located in the University of Bergen (UiB) [28] and University of Oslo (UiO) [29], and support ALICE and ATLAS activities, respectively, which reflects the major research group's involvements in these collaborations. Public grants from Research Council of Norway, in particular from the Nuclear Physics (HENP) and Particle Physics (HEPP) programs, fund the ALICE and ATLAS Tier-1 activities. Typically, these available Tier-1 budgets for ATLAS are ~2.5 MNOK/year, and ~2 MNOK/year for ALICE. These budgets are split 50-50 for hardware purchases and personnel needs. Both universities host several HPC clusters. The Tier-1 resources in Oslo are deployed in the *Abel* cluster [30], and they use ~8% of the available CPU resources in the cluster. In Bergen, the Tier-1 resources are deployed in the *finn* cluster [31], using ~75% of the available CPUs in the cluster. The available budget from public grants in Norway covers ~60% of the total Tier-1 expenses.

Sweden: two HPC centers provide support for Tier-1 activities. The centers are located in the University of Umeå (HPC2N) [32] and in the University of Linköping (NSC) [33]. Both sites mainly support ATLAS Tier-1 activities. Public funds are granted through the Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing (SNIC), submitted to Infrastructure calls. The budgets in the 2015-2017 period are 5.7, 7.2, 6.7 MSEK, respectively. These budgets are split 50-50 between HPC2N and NSC, and they cover the Tier-1 hardware purchases, part of the Tier-1 personnel, and some of the running costs, including the WAN network connectivity costs for the centers. The Tier-1 resources in HPC2N are deployed in the *Abisko* cluster [34], and they use ~3% of the CPU resources in the cluster. In NSC, the Tier-1 resources are deployed in the *Triolith* cluster [35], using ~2.5% of the available CPUs in the cluster. The available budget from public grants in Sweden covers ~60% of the total Tier-1 expenses.

The average funding for the Tier-1 coming from national R&D programs in the Nordic countries is ~1.4 M€/year. Table 4 shows the available and expected budgets for the NDGF-T1 at the different countries, in the period from 2013 to 2017.

NeIC funds Tier-1 personnel across the countries, and the expenses of central NDGF-T1 services hosted at NORDUnet, as well as the main WAN network connectivity of the NDGF-T1. These costs are ~1 M€/year.

R&D programs	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
DK	135	135	135	135	135
FI	130	80	100	80	80
NO	490	490	490	515	515
SE	~	~	620	790	730
Total	>755	>705	1345	1520	1460

Table 4: Available and foreseen Tier-1 budgets (k€) per country from National R&D programs, in the period from 2013 up to 2017.

NDGF-T1 personnel

The NDGF-T1 personnel structure and needs varies in each of the Nordic countries. This personnel is funded either by National R&D programs, NeIC, or in-kind contributions from the HPC centers or Universities, where the Tier-1 resources are deployed. Around 15% of the personnel efforts are spent in development activities for services that are extensively used by the NDGF-T1, such as ARC or dCache. NeIC funds most of these developments activities, but the core of NDGF-T1 personnel costs is related to Tier-1 operations, covering system administration tasks, the experiment liaisons to CERN, the NDGF-T1 security officer, central management tasks and additional local help for tendering and administrative processes.

In order to estimate the operational effort spent in the NDGF-T1, the stakeholders were asked to use a typical FTE value for each of the tasks. The amount of FTE was defined as the ratio between the number of hours spent on the task in a year, divided by 1,600 hours. In order not to be biased, stakeholders were asked to evaluate these efforts from last years of operations experience. Table 5 shows the summary with the total number of Tier-1 FTEs for development and Operations activities, for each of the countries. The table displays how the personnel is financed, i.e. if the personnel is paid by National R&D programs, NeIC, or in-kind from the HPC sites. This table does not include Ph.D. students doing investigations related to Tier-1 activities. A total of 11.35 FTEs are dedicated to Tier-1 Operations activities in the Nordic countries. The stakeholders were also asked for the personnel costs, including all of the possible overheads and benefits. These costs are ~110 k€/year per FTE.

# of FTEs		DK	FI	NO	SE	Total
Development	R&D prog.	-	-	-	-	-
	NeIC	1.00	-	0.50	-	1.50
	In-kind	-	-	0.50	-	0.50
	Total	1.00	-	1.00	-	2.00
Tier-1 Operations	R&D prog.	-	0.50	2.00	2.50	5.00
	NeIC	1.00	1.30	0.50	1.75	4.75
	In-kind	0.30	0.10	1.20	0.20	1.80
	Total	1.30	1.90	3.70	4.45	11.35

Table 5: Personnel distribution (number of FTEs) for Development and Tier-1 Operations activities in the Nordic countries.

Technical descriptions of the sites

By means of the dedicated surveys, technical descriptions and relevant information were gathered from the HPC sites that support the Tier-1 activities. It should be noted that almost all of these sites provided very detailed descriptions on the site internals, answering to ~50 technical questions. The effort spent in filling the questionnaire was highly appreciated. It is impossible to provide all of the details in this report. Hence, the most significant appreciations are listed below, for each of the HPC centers that support the Nordic Tier-1.

NBI: Around 85% of the CPU (AMD Opteron™ 6276) deployed for the Tier-1 is out-of-support. The Tier-1 cannot use other queues at the cluster, so it has a limited number of CPU resources available (~10%) at the site. Two shared tape libraries are installed. The Tier-1 tape capacity is demanding in the site, since it occupies up to 60% of the total tape space that is deployed in the library. Most of the personnel efforts are dedicated to operate the storage (disk and tape) resources. NBI cluster is connected with 2 links of 10 Gbps for LHCOPN and General IP purposes.

CSC: WLCG CPU resources have been migrated to the new *cPouta* IaaS Cloud data center that CSC has deployed in Kajaani. This migration was done in a very transparent way, and it operates very smoothly. The environment deployed is very professional and the support in Finland to WLCG activities is very satisfactory. This IaaS cluster is based on *OpenStack*, and it is equipped with powerful CPUs, lots of memory per node, and fast disks. Users create Virtual Machines (VM) to run their applications, in a similar way this is done in major commercial cloud providers, such as Amazon EC2 [36], MS Azure [37], or Google Cloud [38]. For the moment, the disk resources (dCache nodes) are deployed and operated southern Finland, 500 Kms away from *cPouta* center.

UiB: It supports the ALICE Tier-1 contribution in Norway. The site has deployed many clusters, and the Tier-1 resources fit in less than 3 racks. The Tier-1 uses ~50% of the CPU resources from the *fimm* cluster, which was last upgraded in 2013 (Intel Xeon E5-2650). A shared tape system is deployed, with the Tier-1 using ~10% of the deployed tape capacity. There is a dedicated 10 Gbps link to Oslo.

UiO: It supports the ATLAS Tier-1 contribution in Norway, and the resources are deployed by the University Center for Information Technology (USIT) at the University of Oslo. USIT is a competence institution, formed by a big group of IT professionals, which are as well responsible for the NREN regional center (UNINETT). The Tier-1 CPU resources are provided by the *Abel* cluster, a heterogeneous big cluster (out of two available), which was deployed by 2013. The use of resources by the Tier-1 is typically at ~8% levels. The Tier-1 jobs can use additional resources if the cluster is under low load. This adds +10% of CPU resources, in average. The ARC cache is deployed in 4 NFS-mounted file systems running on a high performance HDS Hitachi Unified Storage VM (HUS-VM) block storage, with a capacity of 48 TiB. A shared tape system is deployed, with the Tier-1 using ~10% of the installed tape capacity. UiO is connected at 10 Gbps to LHCOPN. It is worth mentioning that USIT has 24x7 support for all of the critical elements in the infrastructure.

→ **Note:** Sigma2 [39] is heading the new system for academic computing in Norway. In the new system, the goal is to reduce costs of procurement and operation of national HPC resources, and to put more emphasis on user support and services. The current plan is to reduce the number of HPC installations in Norway to two cost-efficient sites, i.e. two parallel tracks of investments and decommissioning. In this

new scenario, most likely no new resources are expected to be deployed in UiO, neither in UiB. The decommissioning in these centers would occur in some time 2017, and the activities would transition to use resources in the new deployed sites.

HPC2N: The *Abisko* cluster is used to run the Tier-1 activities. Last changes in the cluster were done in 2013, for upgrading the dedicated Tier-1 nodes. The use of resources by the Tier-1 is typically at $\sim 3\%$ levels. The Tier-1 jobs can use additional resources if the cluster is under low load. This adds $+10\%$ of CPU resources, in average. The cluster will be renewed during 2016, with some parts of *Abisko* continuing in production. Two shared tape libraries are installed. The Tier-1 tape capacity is demanding in the site, since it occupies $\sim 50\%$ of the total tape space that is deployed. Most of the personnel efforts are dedicated to operate the storage (disk and tape) resources. HPC2N is connected at 10 Gbps to LHCOPN.

NSC: NSC has a long tradition of HPC resource provisioning in Sweden. The *Triolith* cluster is used to run the Tier-1 activities. The WLCG nodes in the cluster correspond to $\sim 2.5\%$ of the deployed CPU resources. No node sharing and backfilling of WLCG jobs on other parts of the cluster is possible. The last *Triolith* cluster upgrade occurred in 2013. The cluster will be decommissioned by 2017, and a new general-purpose capability cluster will enter production (estimated TCO for the new cluster is $\sim 15\text{M}\text{€}$, a factor ~ 2 of the *Triolith* TCO). A shared tape system is available, with $\sim 25\%$ of the capacity used by the Tier-1. Most of the personnel efforts are dedicated to operate the storage (disk and tape) resources. NSC has a 10 Gbps LHCOPN connection to NORDUnet, via SUNET. This will be soon upgraded to 2x20 Gbps.

Co-hosting on shared resources makes it possible for any project to temporarily utilize much more resources than what is dedicated to the project. The NDGF-T1 is benefiting in some sites from using more CPU than the allocated, or by having better I/O for accessing data on shared tape systems.

Table 6 shows detailed information on CPU deployed at the different HPC sites in December 2015. The total deployed CPU resources accounted up to 41.5 kHSO6 (some estimations are done, since not all of the sites knew or provided the installed capacities in HSO6 units). This represents a small deficit, as compared to the NDGF-T1 pledge, which was 42.1 kHSO6 for the year 2015.

NDGF-T1: CPU Resources							
	kHSO6		# of cores		HSO6/core	GB/core RAM mem.	GB/core Local disk
	ALICE	ATLAS	ALICE	ATLAS			
NBI	3.99*	3.99*	516	516	7.7	3.4	32
CSC	3.1	-	256	-	12.1	2.7	25
UiO	-	6.11	-	800	12.5	4	40
UiB	7.18*	-	704	-	10.2	8	63
HPC2N	-	6.9*	-	480	14.3	2.7	10
NSC	0.6	9.6	40	600	15.9	4	31

Table 6: Technical details on CPU deployed for the NDGF-T1 in December 2015. Some of the values (*) are taken from internal NDGF-T1 2015 planning sheet.

Table 7 shows detailed information on Disk resources deployed at the different HPC sites in December 2015. The total deployed Disk accounted up to 4825 TB (some estimations are done, since not all of the sites provided the installed capacities). This represents a surplus, as compared to the NDGF-T1 pledge, which was 4370 TB for the year 2015. The total ARC cache deployed at the HPC centers, not pledged, is ~ 760 TB, which represents $+17\%$ as compared to the pledged disk deployed in the NDGF-T1.

NDGF-T1: Disk Resources				
	TB		TB	# dCache pools
	ALICE	ATLAS	ARC cache	
NBI	540	540	150	10
CSC	160	-	-	?
UiO	-	1000	48	24
UiB	1050	-	-	29
HPC2N	60*	550*	224	?
NSC	110	810	336	6

Table 7: Technical details on Disk deployed for the NDGF-T1 in December 2015. Some of the values (*) are taken from internal NDGF-T1 2015 planning sheet.

Table 8 shows detailed information on Tape resources deployed at the different HPC centers in December 2015. The table shows, for each HPC site, the total used tape in the tape system unit in which the Tier-1 is co-located, the Tier-1 occupancy in those systems, the number of drives assigned to the Tier-1, the tape system model and tape technologies used. Last column shows the occupancy of Tier-1 space in each of the tape systems. The most intensively used systems by Tier-1 are the ones provided by NBI and HPC2N. The total used tape by the Tier-1 was ~3500 TB. This corresponds to an occupancy of ~80% with respect to the 2015 NDGF-T1 tape pledge, set to a value of 4330 TB.

NDGF-T1: Tape Resources							
	TOTAL TB	T1 TB	# of T1 drives	Tech.	Model	Ext. frames	Occupancy
NBI	1800	1040	4 (dedicated)	LT06	IBM TS3500	4	58%
CSC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
UiO	5000	576	4 (dedicated)	3592JC	Spectra Logic T-Finity	-	12%
UiB	1700	200	4 (dedicated)	LT04	?	?	12%
HPC2N	1900	1030	6 (shared)	LT05	IBM TS3500	5	54%
NSC	4500	665	16 (shared)	LT05/LT06	IBM TS3500	8	15%

Table 8: Technical details on Tape deployed for the NDGF-T1 in December 2015.

Cluster electricity costs estimations

Sites were asked to provide the electricity costs associated to the Tier-1 services running at the sites. This is an extremely complex measure, since it needs a very good understanding of the IT infrastructure and cooling consumes. This is a typical unknown for data centers co-located in Universities, where the electricity bills are typically paid by third parties. It is also common than even the payers don't know in detail these costs, since the electricity bills can contain consumes from many installations, without detailed information of who generates the expenses. The sites benefit from distributed cold water-cooling available from towns, whose indirect costs are difficult to estimate as well.

Some of the sites provided detailed information on the total cluster electricity costs. Others provided the IT consumes of the CPU clusters. Others were not able to provide any meaningful value. For those who provided a value, and applying factors to correct for the internal cluster shares of the Tier-1, a rough value for the Tier-1 electricity costs were calculated.

The most significant consumes come from the deployed CPU and Disk resources. Since most of the hardware for the Tier-1 in the HPC centers was deployed in ~2013, one can estimate the current deployed resources consumes elsewhere by taking the

capacities deployed and which were the typical consumes of CPU and Disk resources in 2013. Powers of 2 W/HS06 and 6 W/TB for CPU and Disk, respectively, can be taken as references (see next section for details). Evaluated powers need to be corrected by cooling and other overhead contributions. This is typically measured by the *Power Usage Effectiveness* (PUE) [40], which is the ratio of total amount of energy used by a computer data center facility to the energy delivered to computing equipment. This value shows seasonal variations along the year. Some of the sites provided estimation of PUE ranges, being 1.25 a reasonable average value. The total Tier-1 facility consumes can be evaluated from the deployed Tier-1 IT equipment powers, scaled up with the PUE factor. The yearly-consumed kWh can easily be translated to electricity costs, by applying the electricity price at each of the countries. Table 9 shows the electricity prices in the Nordic countries for 2015, as reported by the sites and values reported by Eurostat [41]. The average electricity price (industrial and household) for 2015 was ~0.15 €/kWh.

Electricity price €/KWh		From Surveys €/kWh	Eurostat		
Country	Center		Household €/kWh	Industrial €/kWh	Average €/kWh
DK	NBI	0.20	0.30	0.09	0.20
FI	CSC	-	0.15	0.07	0.11
NO	UiO	0.09	0.165	0.08	0.12
	UiB	-			
SE	NSC	0.12	0.18	0.075	0.13
	HPC2N	0.14			

Table 9: Reported electricity costs (€/kWh) for the NDGF-T1 HPC centers, and electricity costs obtained from Eurostat.

Table 10 shows the 2015 Tier-1 electricity costs as derived from the information provided by the HPC sites, and the evaluated costs for each site. Assuming that the reported December 2015 installed resources were available during the year, the total electricity cost for the NDGF-T1 is ~180 k€. However, the installed resources could have varied during the year. In particular, the resources deployed until March 2015 could have followed the NDGF-T1 2014 pledges. Applying this correction a value of ~175 k€ is derived for the Tier-1 electricity costs in 2015. A typical consume of ~2 kW for each tape system, and for each of the sites (weighted to the fraction of Tier-1 tape system usage), has been added in the model. The averaged power for the 2015 NDGF-T1 deployed resources is ~115 kW (CPU: 82 kW, Disk: 33 kW).

Electricity costs		From Surveys	Estimated
Country	Center	Cost (k€/year)	Cost (k€/year)
DK	NBI	~70	48
FI	CSC	-	8
NO	UiO	>20	23
	UiB	-	27
SE	NSC	>15	38
	HPC2N	>7	30
Total		>125	~175

Table 10: Electricity costs (k€) for the Tier-1 resources deployed at the NDGF-T1 centers, derived from the reported clusters consumptions, and estimated (modelled) electricity costs (k€).

WAN network costs

The WLCG Tier-1 centers hold 50% of all of the data that is present in WLCG. The Wide-Area-Networks (WAN) at the Tier-1 centers are heavily used, and the generated traffic is normally at the higher positions at NREN monitors for all of the countries that host a Tier-1 center. Since these network needs are very demanding, large bandwidth links are deployed at the Tier-1s. Thus, connectivity goes from 10 Gbps up to 100 Gbps, which is deployed at some (big) Tier-1 centers. A private star-structured network, the so-called LHCOPN [8], interconnects the globally distributed Tier-1 centers and the Tier-0. A similar private network to interconnect Tier-1 with Tier-2 centers (LHCONE) is being as well deployed [42]. Since the LHC experiments deployed global storage federations based on the *XRootD* protocol [43], all of the Tier-1s have naturally become data servers to all of the WLCG sites. Data can be remotely accessed by any WLCG center worldwide.

These constraints apply for the NDGF-T1, and in particular, good connectivity between the HPC centers that conform the NDGF-T1 should be as well established. NeIC funds some central connectivity costs for the NDGF-T1, through NORDUnet. In 2015, this included the deployment of LHCOPN connectivity at 10 Gbps for the NDGF-T1 as a whole, an additional 10 Gbps connection to IJS, the cost related to host central services for the Tier-1¹, any hardware related costs, and the maintenance and operations costs for these services. The total amount was 394 k€. It is worth mentioning that the 24x7 support, attendance to LHCOPN meetings, and operations efforts are included in these costs. Around 1.4 FTE-equivalent is outsourced at NORDUnet to cope with these NDGF-T1 network activities. Since this was not included in the previously calculated NDGF-T1 Operations effort (11.35 FTEs), the effective Operations effort at the NDGF-T1 is 12.75 FTEs.

These associated network costs for the HPC centers that conform the NDGF-T1 can be either covered by the National R&D projects, the HPC sites, the Universities, or directly by the NRENs. Each country manages this in different ways. Sweden charges the network costs (~100 k€/year) directly to the National R&D programs. In other countries, either the NRENs or the sites cover the costs. The point where NORDUnet delivers a country link can have a direct effect on the network costs. HPC2N, NSC, and UiB are ‘remote’ centers to these links, and UiO, CSC and NBI are better positioned towards these country links. Taking the Sweden example, we can consider an average price for a ‘remote’ center of ~50k€/year, and assume a reduced ~20 k€/year for ‘nearby’ centers. This gives a very rough estimation of the in-kind external network costs for the sites in which this information is not known. Table 11 shows the costs breakdown for the NDGF-T1 external network. The total inferred WAN costs for the NDGF-T1 are ~550 k€/year (20% in-kind contributed).

(2015)		Cost (k€/year)
NeIC	Tier-1 Hardware & Services	46
	LHCOPN Hardware & Services	170
	Maintenance	26
	Operations	152 (1.4 FTE-equiv.)
SE	NORDUnet link	40
	SUNET links to 2 sites	65
FI, NO, DK	(in-kind) Links to 4 sites	~20* ~70* ~20*

Table 11: Costs for central Tier-1 services hosted by NORDUnet, and LHCOPN network costs covered by NeIC (general Tier-1 connection) and by SNIC in Sweden. In-kind (estimated *) contributions in other countries are shown.

¹ dCache nodes, perfSONAR-PS, Vidyo...

² ARC-CEs, ARC caches, dCache pools, AliEn, CVMFS, squid proxies, Tier-1 monitoring tools, ...

Infrastructure and Generic Services

At the different HPC sites, there are inherent Tier-1 costs associated to the infrastructure, costs associated to the Tier-1 generic services², and costs related to maintenance of the equipment.

Some of the centers are charged by renting fees to cover the infrastructure expenses. In NSC, the renting is based on peak power consumption (at 0.07 €/kWh). In HPC2N, this renting cost was ~700 kSEK in 2015. In UiO, the fee is calculated based on the occupied area, with a cost of 1250 €/m²/year. Applying the Tier-1 shares in these centers, the infrastructure costs for the Tier-1 are ~ 9 k€/year, ~11 k€/year, and ~34 k€/year, respectively. These 3 sites provide ~50% of the total NDGF-T1 resources. Extrapolating, the infrastructure costs of the NDGF-T1 are ~100 k€/year.

These sites reported the costs for Tier-1 generic services. With a similar approach, we can estimate that ~50 k€/year is spent in generic Tier-1 services at the sites.

All of the big hardware purchases include in-situ service and maintenance. Even though, small costs associated to maintenance and repairs are present. The reported costs from the sites accounts for a small contribution of ~15 k€/year for maintenance costs of the NDGF-T1 services.

2015 NDGF-T1 costs breakdown

In light of these values and estimations, the NDGF-T1 total cost and the costs breakdown can be determined, for the year 2015, grouped in different categories:

[A] Resources:

Most of the Tier-1 CPU, Disk, and Tape resources are funded from R&D programs, at all of the countries, with a budget of ~650 k€/year. The sites that allow a flexible exploitation of the CPU clusters, in-kind contribute to the Tier-1. Typically, these contributions add +10% over the site pledges at the sites. Taking the reference €/HSO6 value for 2013 (see next section), we can convert these contributions to in-kind costs to the Tier-1 (this amounts to ~20 k€/year). This category does not include the in-kind disk from IJS.

[B] Electricity:

Estimated to ~175 k€/year.

[C] Infrastructure & Generic services:

This category includes the overall estimated value of ~165 k€/year. The costs for the central Tier-1 services deployed by NORDUnet are added here (46k€/year), as well as the NORDUnet costs associated to maintenance (26k€/year). HPC2N charges 100 kSEK to SNIC; the remaining is in-kind provided to the Tier-1 project.

[D] Network:

This category includes the network costs covered by NeIC, the costs charged to SNIC at Swedish sites, and estimated in-kind contributions from NRENs and/or sites.

[E] Personnel & travels:

This category includes all of the personnel funded by National R&D projects, in-kind contributions from the sites, NORDUnet Operations efforts, and NeIC personnel. An

² ARC-CEs, ARC caches, dCache pools, AliEn, CVMFS, squid proxies, Tier-1 monitoring tools, ...

additional personnel that helps with tenders and administrative tasks at the sites is considered for each site. These efforts are small, 0.1-0.2 FTEs per site. The development efforts (215k€/year) are not shown in this category, only the personnel costs associated to the Tier-1 Operations. NeIC contributes with the most significant budget for travels (~110 k€/year).

→ **Note:** VAT is normally deducted in hardware purchases that are made in Denmark and Sweden, but this is not the case for Finland and Norway. VAT in the Nordic countries is ~25%. This has an impact for some of the acquired Tier-1 hardware, which results a bit more expensive in some of the countries.

		DK	FI	NO		SE		NeIC					Total	
		NBI	CSC	UiB	UiO	HPC2N	NSC	FI	NO	DK	SE	Network		Others
A	R&D Prog.	135	25	140	140	108	108	-	-	-	-	-	-	655
	In-kind	-	14*	-	3*	2*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20
B	R&D Prog.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	In-kind	48*	8*	27*	24*	30*	38*	-	-	-	-	-	-	175
C	R&D Prog.	-	-	-	-	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	72	83
	In-kind	41*	16*	37*	31*	26*	37*	-	-	-	-	-	-	154
D	R&D Prog.	-	-	-	-	53	53	-	-	-	-	170	-	275
	In-kind	20*	20*	50*	20*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	110
E	R&D Prog.	-	55	105	105	138	138	143	53	110	193	152	110	1300
	In-kind	44	22	63	63	22	22	-	-	-	-	-	-	236
Total													~3.0M€	

Table 12: NDGF-T1 costs, per categories, countries and funding origins. Some of the values (*) are estimates, based from partial real costs or based on model. See text for details.

In 2015, the total cost of the NDGF-T1 was ~3 M€. Figure 18 shows the costs breakdown per country, by funding origins. As expected, the cost per country scales with the capacities delivered to the NDGF-T1. In Norway and Sweden, up to 60% of the Tier-1 costs are funded by the National R&D programs. NeIC contributes with 50% and 6% of total costs in Finland and Norway, respectively, and ~25% in the other countries. Both in Norway and Denmark, the in-kind contributions cover up to ~38% of the total Tier-1 costs in the country. Figure 19 shows the costs at the countries, for each of the categories. In Finland, up to 75% of the budget is spent in personnel. Figure 21 and Figure 21 show the total NDGF-T1 costs breakdown for each of the categories described above, and the total costs per funding origin. Half of the NDGF-T1 costs are related to personnel, and ~23% of NDGF-T1 costs are in-kind contributions from sites.

Figure 18: (left) NDGF-T1 2015 costs breakdown per country and funding origins (right) relative contributions in each of the countries by funding origins.

Figure 19: (left) NDGF-T1 2015 costs breakdown per country and category (right) relative contributions in each of the countries and category.

NDGF-T1 costs: categories (2015)

Figure 20: NDGF-T1 2015 total costs per category

NDGF-T1 costs: funding origins (2015)

Figure 21: NDGF-T1 2015 total costs, for each funding origin.

We can compare these results with the average costs breakdown from the EU e-FISCAL project study [44], as shown in Figure 22, when analysing the costs of several European computing centers in the year 2011. Even if this study did not covered the (external) network costs, a rough comparison says that, in average, the structural expenses obtained in this NDGF-T1 model are very similar to other centers placed in Europe. The average FTE costs in EU is ~46k€/year, including overheads.

Figure 22: e-FISCAL EU studies for 2011 costs (typical IT infrastructures).

Estimation of tape systems costs

Many tape libraries are available in the HPC sites and used by the Tier-1 activities. These systems are built from a common frame, most of them flexible to grow depending on the needs, equipped with all of the necessary tape drives, front-ends and the magnetic tapes to hold the data. All of the deployed systems are shared with other scientific communities. Typically, IBM TSM3500 tape libraries, with 4 to 8 expansion frames, are deployed in the HPC sites that support the NDGF-T1. In HPC2N and NBI the tape systems are driven by the Tier-1 needs (with occupancies >50%, based on actual use, ignoring empty tapes assigned to the project). For the rest of the sites, the Tier-1 occupancy in the tape libraries is at ~10% levels.

Since these systems are shared, it is particularly difficult to estimate the actual costs for deploying the Tier-1 tape needs for the NDGF-T1. However, since most of the sites use the same tape system model, we can make an estimation of the total tape infrastructure costs, by taking into account the deployed libraries and expansion frames costs, the costs of the drives and front-ends, the amortization of these systems (assuming 8 years for the tape libraries, and 6 years for the tape drives and front-ends), and the utilization share by the Tier-1 at each of the HPC centers. Table 13 shows the estimated infrastructural costs (tape libraries, drives and front-ends), assuming an initial cost of ~40 k€ for the tape library, ~25 k€ for each expansion frame, ~15k€ for each of the drives, and ~1 k€/year for each front-end.

The estimated costs of the deployed tape system for the NDGF-T1 are ~30 k€/year for the libraries, ~45 k€/year for all of the drives used by the Tier-1 (~18 drives, taking into account the shares and/or dedicated drives), and ~18 k€/year for the tape front-ends. The tape cartridges costs are not included in this evaluation. This total evaluated cost of ~90 k€/year would be equivalent to the running cost of a single IBM TS3500 system equipped with 8 extension frames and 18 drives.

	Occupancy		Estimated system costs (k€/year)			€/TB
	T1 TB	% Library	Library	Drives	Front-ends	
NBI	1040	58%	10	10	4	23
CSC	-	-	-	-	-	-
UiO	576	12%	2	10	4	28
UiB	200	12%	2	10	4	80
HPC2N	1030	54%	11	8	3	21
NSC	665	15%	4	6	2	18
Total	3511		30	44	18	

Table 13: Technical details on Tape deployed for the NDGF-T1 in December 2015.

A single system with 10 drives and 5 expansion frames could hold and cope with all of the NDGF-T1 current data. The cost of such a system would be ~55 k€/year. The costs reduction is not very significant, of the order ~35 k€/year. In other words, there is an extra-cost of +35k€/year for using the 5 distributed tape systems in the current NDGF-T1 configuration. This cost corresponds to ~1% of the yearly Tier-1 budget.

Findings and recommendations

Finding #4.1: The evaluated total 2015 cost for the NDGF-T1 is ~3.0 M€. Around ~43% of the Tier-1 costs are financed by National R&D Programs. NeIC finances ~34% of the costs. In-kind contributions from sites/NRENs add up ~23% of the total Tier-1 costs.

Finding # 4.2: Additional +20% of disk space with respect to the NDGF-T1 WLCG disk pledge needs to be deployed to run the ATLAS ARC caches. If these caches were deployed in supported hardware, this would represent an additional cost of ~50 k€/year. Recommendation: keep a closer eye on the deployed caches performance, since it can affect to the performance of I/O demanding jobs run at the sites. If possible, improve the cache performances in the largest ATLAS HPC sites. The effect in the total Tier-1 budget would be small.

Finding #4.3: NeIC covers the NDGF-T1 WAN network costs (as a whole). National R&D programs cover the WAN network costs of Sweden sites. Around 30% of the WAN Tier-1 network costs are in-kind contributions from sites/NRENs. The total WAN network costs in the current NDGF-T1 configuration is 385 k€/year. This corresponds to ~13% of the Tier-1 budget.

Finding #4.4: The number of FTEs to operate the current configuration of the NDGF-T1 is slightly higher than in other similar Tier-1s, due to its distributed nature. The costs of this specialized personnel in the Nordic countries are a factor 2.4 higher than those in Europe, according to the e-fiscal EU study.

Finding #4.5: The cost of the distributed tape libraries have been addressed. Taking into account the amortization time of the five used tape libraries, and the number of drives used by the Tier-1, the over-costs for using these systems is ~35 k€/year, as compared to the cost of having only one tape system coping with the Tier-1 needs. The reason is that many systems are shared with other disciplines. Only at two sites the tape system is used at ~50% levels by the Tier-1 activities.

Finding #4.6: In all of the Nordic countries, the funding for Tier-1 computing resources comes from calls to national R&D programs. The computing needs are typically embedded in big R&D and Physics projects. The costs of computing resources for a Tier-1 are high, hence it is important to properly justify and defend the computing needs in all of the countries. Recommendation: since this way to obtain funding is highly competitive, the computing competences in the different countries should be re-enforced, otherwise this might have a negative impact in future Tier-1 funds obtained by this means.

5. Single-site NDGF-T1: costs model

One can model the cost of the NDGF-T1 if it would have been deployed as a single site. This evaluation is not a full TCO, as it assumes that the NDGF-T1 had been deployed in an already existing center, which had scaled up with the Tier-1 needs.

NDGF-T1 provides services to two of the LHC experiments, ALICE and ATLAS, accounting for 9% and 6% of the total Tier-1 resources, respectively. The NDGF-T1 pledges to WLCG as computed by applying these shares are shown in Table 14.

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
CPU (kHSo6)	12.1	13.7	18.3	25.8	29.0	34.0	42.1	45.1
Disk (TB)	1580	1720	1964	2690	2710	3830	4370	4710
Tape (TB)	1660	1770	2566	3672	4280	3190	4330	6770

Table 14: NDGF-T1 ALICE+ATLAS pledges, targeting 9% and 6% of total Tier-1 resources, respectively.

Taking into account the decommissioning of equipment (4 years lifetime) and the growth profile to keep with the pledges, an estimation of the capacity to buy can be derived, for each of the years (deployed capacity since 2006 is considered). Table 15 shows the capacity to buy each year in order to keep with the NDGF-T1 pledges.

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
CPU (kHSo6)	3.0	2.8	8.2	11.7	6.3	7.8	16.3	14.7
Disk (TB)	395	298	718	1279	415	1418	1258	1619
Tape (TB)	415	276	1294	1687	1023	0	1620	4127

Table 15: NDGF-T1 capacity ramp-up of resources to keep with the ALICE+ATLAS pledges, assuming a resources lifetime of 4 years.

In order to estimate the cost of executing these capacity purchases, one can use the equipment cost estimations made by Bernd Panzer-Steindel, from CERN IT department (Bernd-model [45]). This document, based in real purchases made by CERN, was written in May 2012 in order to foresee the cost evolution of future equipment. The ratio of price/performance of computer equipment decreases over time and these estimations fit quite well with purchases made at CERN, and many other Tier-1 centers, up to current dates. Figure 23 shows the cost estimations for CPU, Disk and Tape (LTO technology), and the actual costs obtained by several tenders at PIC Tier-1 and NDGF-T1. The Bernd-model assumes that the purchases are anticipated, due to tendering processes, in order to have the systems in time (at least, ~6 months in advance). VAT is not included in these estimations. Table 16 shows the cost estimations, by year, for CPU, Disk and Tape resources.

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
€/HSo6	133.4	78.3	38.2	24.4	19.1	15.1	11.8	9.9	8.9	7.2
€/TB Disk	2037	1412	824.5	518.1	390.2	355.4	308.9	272.7	257.0	211.0
€/TB Tape	335.4	220.1	198.7	217.4	142.3	37.2	28.5	20.7	18.7	18.3

Table 16: CERN cost estimations provided by B. Panzer (Bernd-model), for CPU, Disk and Tape resources.

Figure 23: CPU, Disk and Tape prices (without VAT) according to the Bernd-model, and real purchases prices from PIC and NDGF-T1 Tier-1 centers.

Figure 24: CPU and Disk consumes, modelled according to real hardware consumes from PIC Tier-1 purchases.

In order to estimate the electricity costs to operate such resources, we need to model the hardware consumes for the CPU, Disk and Tape resources. Since a Tier-1 is typically buying resources in a yearly basis, one can take any Tier-1 as a reference to model the consume costs. Figure 24 shows the CPU and Disk consumes for PIC Tier-1 purchases, since 2007, which are used to model the CPU and Disk consumes in terms of W/HS06 and W/TB. The tape systems consume typically 2 kW in average, which is

a very negligible contribution, at the order of 1%-3% in this model. The average PUE in the Nordic sites is 1.25, and the average electricity cost ~0.15 €/kWh.

There are other additional costs that should be taken into account in this model, such as VAT for hardware purchases, additional costs on Tape system, costs for infrastructure upgrades and general services, WAN network costs, the average number of FTEs (including 24x7 support) operating the Tier-1, and travels budget.

Single-site NDGF-T1 costs breakdown [2009-2015]

[A] Resources:

Capacity ramp-ups costs are evaluated using the Bernd-model. VAT is normally deducted in purchases that are made in Denmark and Sweden, but this is not the case for Finland and Norway. Applying 25% of VAT for hardware purchases yields to an increase of the Tier-1 budget of ~130 k€/year. Additional resources costs, inherent to Tape systems, refer to the migration of data from old to new tape technology or the introduction of new tape drives and front-ends in the system. A yearly cost of ~50 k€/year, as discussed in section 4, is considered.

[B] Electricity:

Estimated from deployed hardware consumes, average PUE of 1.25, and average electricity price of ~0.15 €/kWh.

[C] Infrastructure & Generic services:

Costs related to generic services and maintenances are reduced here (in comparison to the current distributed NDGF-T1 costs), since there are fewer services (less redundant) to be provided. No ARC caches are needed for ATLAS. Since ~20% of the deployed disk is provisioned as cache, this corresponds to ~50 k€/year savings, if one is deploying caches in maintained hardware, under warranty. Since this is not the case in the current NDGF-T1, the later reduction is not applied, but it gives the estimation of how expensive it would be to run the ARC caches in such a scenario.

By considering the deployed generic Tier-1 services at the HPC sites, a reduction of ~30% of costs might be expected in this model. Additional saving of -35k€/year can be applied, since only one tape system is deployed in this model (see section 4 for details). The costs in this category are around ~180 k€/year.

[D] Network:

The NDGF-T1 should be connected to the rest of the Tiers in the WLCG structure by means of a dedicated LHCOPN, LHCONE and general-purpose network. Taking into account the pure current (central) network costs, that would apply for a single-site, the expenditures in this category are ~170 k€/year.

[E] Personnel & travels:

WLCG Operations Coordination group assessed the Operational efforts in the WLCG sites in early 2014 [46]. The average number of FTEs to operate a Tier-1 was determined to be around 12 FTEs, but this is largely coupled to the size of the center. A more realistic number for a Tier-1 of the size of the NDGF-T1 should be around 7.5 FTEs, assuming that the (external) network support continues outsourced to NORDUnet (~1.4 equivalent FTEs). To achieve the stringent availability targets for a Tier-1, a 24x7 incident response service should be established by means of 24x7 support. Typically this takes up to 0.5 FTE at a Tier-1. With an average cost of 110k€/year/person, including overheads and benefits, and considering ~100k€/year for travels, the costs in this category are ~1.1 M€/year.

Table 17 shows the costs breakdown for this NDGF-T1 deployment model, since 2009. The Tier-1 yearly cost is stable at ~10% levels, mainly due to the fact that the LHC experiment requirements are based in a flat-budget model [47]. Since new systems are being introduced every year, with better consumes, the derived electricity cost in 2015 in this model is slightly better as compared the one evaluated for the current NDGF-T1 configuration (since most of the resources were procured by 2013). The average cost for operating the NDGF-T1 in this configuration is ~2.3 M€/year.

		2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
A	CPU	116	68	158	176	74	77	145
	Disk	326	154	280	455	128	387	323
	Tape	132	110	234	113	79	50	80
	HW VAT	144	83	168	186	70	129	137
B		256	223	245	230	164	156	156
C		180	180	180	180	180	180	180
D		170	170	170	170	170	170	170
E		1132	1132	1132	1132	1132	1132	1132
Total		2456	2121	2566	2641	1998	2281	2324
							Average	2.3 M€/year

Table 17: Single-site NDGF-T1 derived costs, per categories. These values are estimates, based from partial real costs or based on model. See text for details.

In comparison to the current NDGF-T1 distributed model, this centralized deployment offers a reduction of the Tier-1 costs up to ~0.7 M€/year. This would correspond to a reduction of the current Tier-1 budget by ~23%.

The main savings in this single-site model are related to manpower needs, reduced network costs, since the network costs to interconnect sites are not present, and a reduction on the infrastructure (tape systems) and generic Tier-1 services costs. In comparison to the current distributed model, the costs reductions would be ~375 k€/year (~3.4 FTEs) for manpower, ~215 k€/year for the network cost, and ~60 k€/year for infrastructure and generic services costs. The single-site NDGF-T1 costs breakdown for the year 2015 is shown in Figure 25.

NDGF-T1 single-site costs: categories (2015)

Figure 25: Estimated single-site NDGF-T1 costs per category, for the year 2015.

We can compare these results to the PIC Tier-1 running costs, since it is of similar size as the NDGF-T1. In December 2015, the deployed resources in PIC Tier-1 were: 49.5 kHSo6 for CPU, 3950 TB for Disk, and 9876 TB for Tape. PIC Tier-1 has been analysing in detail its cost expenditure since 2008. In 2015, the PIC Tier-1 had a cost of ~1.6 M€. The PIC Tier-1 center runs with fewer personnel than the typical average Tier-1, due to the high-level of automation that is present, easing operations and reducing manpower needs. A total of ~8 FTEs operate the center, at an average value of 45 k€/year/person, including overheads and benefits. PIC Tier-1 can deduct the VAT from hardware purchases. Even if there is a cost to connect to the NREN link, the site does not cover further NREN associated costs. If the personnel costs in Spain were similar to the personnel costs in the Nordic countries, the PIC Tier-1 and the estimated single-site NDGF-T1 costs would be at almost the same levels.

The Bernd-model for hardware purchases applied to the PIC Tier-1 yields to results that are valid in a range that varies from 15% to 20% (for the costs listed in category A). This is dominated from the actual Disk costs and the modelled values (higher). Hence, this single-site NDGF-T1 model presented here should be considered with ~5% of accuracy.

Findings and recommendations

Finding #5.1: The derived electricity cost in this single-site NDGF-T1 model for the year 2015 is ~155 k€. The estimated electricity costs of the current NDGF-T1 distributed configuration were estimated to be ~175 k€/year, slightly bigger since the current NDGF-T1 operates hardware, which most of it was procured by 2013.

Finding #5.2: The single-site NDGF-T1 model presents a cost-effective scenario in terms of manpower, network and infrastructure costs, if compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1 scenario. Generic Tier-1 services costs reduce, as well as the costs for the tape systems, since in this scenario the Tier-1 use only one tape library.

Finding #5.3: Even if there are savings in many categories, still this single-site model shows that ~50% of the Tier-1 budget is spent in personnel. Personnel costs are high in the Nordic countries, if one compares to the average EU value quoted by the e-fiscal study (~46 k€/year, for one FTE).

Finding #5.4: The estimated 2015 in-kind contributions from HPC centers to the current distributed NDGF-T1 are about ~0.7M€/year. The savings that would present a centralized solution are at the same levels than the current in-kind contributions from sites to the current NDGF-T1 configuration.

6. Intermediate costs models for the NDGF-T1

Intermediate solutions for a cost-effective NDGF-T1 could be applied, preserving all of the countries participation in the Tier-1 project. This section describes the costs for deploying the NDGF-T1 with only 1 HPC center per country, an scenario in which the countries tender and purchase the hardware that is finally deployed in a single-site placed in a Nordic country, and another scenario in which the resources are distributed as of now, but centralizing all of the Tier-1 Operations to the NeIC Operations team.

Scenario 1: 1 HPC center per country

This scenario assumes 1 HPC center per country. Since all of the resources deployed for the NDGF-T1 are the same, neither the costs on resources or electricity would substantially reduce (the values from the model described in section 5 are considered). The major benefits for such a configuration would be a cost-effective configuration in terms of personnel, infrastructure, generic Tier-1 services and network costs.

[C] Infrastructure & Generic services:

As in the single-site configuration, the costs related to generic Tier-1 services and maintenances are reduced here, since there are less redundant services to be provided. A reduction of ~15% of costs might be expected in this configuration for generic Tier-1 services. Additional savings of -15k€/year can be applied, since only 3 tape systems would be deployed in this model. Taking 2015 costs as a reference, the costs in this category are ~210 k€/year.

[D] Network:

Reducing the number of HPC centers reduces the costs to interconnect the distributed sites that conform the Tier-1. The average (external) network costs per site in 2015 were ~35 k€/year (see section 4 for details). This intermediate model would result in ~70 k€/year savings for network costs, as compared to the current NDGF-T1 configuration. The costs in this category are ~310 k€/year.

[E] Personnel & travels:

For the currently distributed NDGF-T1, the Tier-1 Operations personnel accounts to 11.35 FTEs. Averaging this effort for all of the current sites, this model with 1 HPC center per country would reduce the personnel needs by -3.8 FTEs. However, to be more realistic, and aligned with the findings that will be shown in section 8, all of the current sites want to have participation in the Tier-1 activities, even if they do not run/operate services. Hence, we can assume at least a participation of 0.5 FTE from those sites that previously had offered resources. Hence, a more realistic view of total Tier-1 personnel needs in this scenario would be ~8.5 FTEs. The personnel costs are reduced by ~290k€/year. The costs in this category are estimated at ~1.2 M€/year.

The average cost for operating the Tier-1 in this configuration would be ~2.6 M€/year. In comparison to the current NDGF-T1 distributed model, this model with 1 HPC center per country offers a reduction of the Tier-1 costs up to ~0.4 M€/year. This would correspond to a reduction of the current Tier-1 budget by ~13%. The NDGF-T1 costs breakdown for this model with 1 HPC center per country, for the year 2015, is shown in Figure 26.

NT1 1 site per country: categories (2015)

Figure 26: NDGF-T1 costs per category, in the scenario with only 1 HPC center per country, for the year 2015.

Scenario 2: a single-site with resources bought from each of the countries

This scenario assumes a single-site deployed in one of the Nordic countries, populated with hardware that has been previously tendered and purchased by each of the Nordic countries/sites. This scenario assumes that the equipment is finally delivered to the site that hosts the NDGF-T1, and that this can (legally) be done. This model is not very different as the one considered in Section 5. There is additional manpower to keep competences at the sites that previously had offered resources to the Tier-1, and additional personnel at the sites needed for tendering and administration processes.

[A] Resources:

The same costs as evaluated in Section 5 (single-site model) are considered here.

[B] Electricity:

The same costs as evaluated in Section 5 (single-site model) are considered here.

[C] Infrastructure & Generic services:

The same costs as evaluated in Section 5 (single-site model) are considered here.

[D] Network:

The same costs as evaluated in Section 5 (single-site model) are considered here.

[E] Personnel & travels:

The same costs as evaluated in Section 5 (single-site model) are considered here, with additional 0.5 FTE from those sites that previously had offered resources, and additional site personnel that is still needed for tendering and administration processes, estimated to be about ~0.1 FTE for each of the sites. The total Tier-1 personnel needs in this scenario would be ~9.5 FTEs. The costs in this category are estimated at ~1.5 M€/year.

The average cost for operating the Tier-1 in this configuration would be ~2.7 M€/year. In comparison to the current NDGF-T1 distributed model, this model offers a reduction of the Tier-1 costs up to ~0.3 M€/year. This would correspond to a reduction of the current Tier-1 budget by ~10%. The NDGF-T1 costs breakdown for this model, for the year 2015, is shown in Figure 27.

NDGF-T1 "shipping to a" single-site costs: categories (2015)

Figure 27: NDGF-T1 costs per category, in the scenario with a single-site deployed in a Nordic country, with hardware tendered and purchased from the current NDGF-T1 sites, for the year 2015.

Scenario 3: Distributed resources – centralized operations

This scenario would only reduce personnel in a marginal way, since one still would need the help from the site to tender, and have good deployment, access and operation of the deployed resources. It is very unlikely that a central team would have full access to configure and manage the deployed resources. Also, sites would still want to have participation in the Tier-1 activities (as mentioned before, at ~0.5 FTE levels for each of the current sites).

The current NeIC Operations team is composed by 4.55 FTEs. Assuming that half of the current Tier-1 FTE efforts that are paid by National R&D programs are embedded to the central NeIC team (~2.4 FTEs) and adding 0.5 FTE contributions for each of the sites, this would yield to ~10 FTEs for Tier-1 Operations. This would correspond to a reduction of -1.1 FTE, in comparison to the current distributed NDGF-T1 scenario. This provides a marginal saving of -125 k€/year, as compared to the current Tier-1 budget of ~3.0 M€/year. The costs reduction would be at ~4% levels.

Findings and recommendations

Finding #6.1: Deploying the NDGF-T1 with only 1 HPC center per country offers savings up to ~13%, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1 scenario with 6 HPC sites in 4 countries. Recommendation: Since Norway is reducing the number of HPC clusters in the country, it is highly recommended to deploy the Tier-1 in only 1 site, to reduce personnel, network, and redundant services overheads.

Finding #6.2: Deploying a single-site in the Nordic countries, with hardware tendered and purchased from each of the current sites that conform the NDGF-T1 would offer savings up to ~10%, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1 scenario with 6 HPC sites in 4 countries.

Finding #6.3: A model in which all of the Operations efforts are centralized to the NeIC Operations team has been addressed. To be realistic, this model would not offer a significant reduction of costs.

7. Evaluation of the non-monetary aspects

The NDGF-T1 has a very successful history participating as a Tier-1 in WLCG. Both ALICE and ATLAS activities are carried out very smoothly and efficiently at the Tier-1 site. This is commendable, since the NDGF-T1 is the only Tier-1 built from resources spread in many countries and HPC sites. The expertise towards unique goals and service delivery has been built from a group of people spread in four countries. The tasks performed by this group ensure the viability and success of the Tier-1 activities in the Nordic region.

The participation in the Tier-1 activities is seen as highly strategic for the countries, the LHC researchers and the resource providers. From one side, this participation allows improving the quality of the LHC research activities in the Nordic countries, since the skilled computing team from the Tier-1 is instrumental for advice and help to scientists, which allows for efficient exploitation of the computing resources. It also allows gaining Grid competences, which are beneficial to other science and technology fields. The strong reliability targets imposed for the Tier-1 services help the HPC sites in building infrastructures that are very efficient and stable, for all of the disciplines they support.

The involvement in Tier-1 activities helps the HPC sites to get funding, and in particular, personnel that can later help transferring this knowledge to other disciplines. Many scientific fields are expecting large growth rates of their data volumes and they seek local, national and international advice. The role of the Tier-1 team is to strategically transfer their expertise to these activities, hence improving the quality for the services delivered. Additionally, the team can help in transfer of knowledge to industry on commercial provisioning of science-optimized, high data throughput services.

The WLCG global strategy for the next years is to work towards integration, federation and virtualization of resources. This will involve an intense program of international collaboration with distinguished groups around the world. In addition, resources from HPC centers will be integrated (more and more) in an opportunistic fashion, as well as elastic growth through Cloud resources, aligning with European Union and U.S. strategies. The NDGF-T1 team can play an important role in all of these activities, since they operate a unique federated Tier-1. Their competences and experiences can be extremely useful for other sites in WLCG, in particular to other Tier-1 centers, when dealing with these new features.

Additionally, the NDGF-T1 has built a very fruitful cooperation between development and operations activities, in both directions. The development activities in *ARC middleware* and *dCache* are important for the next R&D challenges that WLCG needs to face. ARC brings built-in functionalities to federate resources, and the NDGF-T1 team has a very excellent record in operating a distributed dCache storage system. It is expected that the NDGF-T1 is actively participating or leading some of these R&D activities in WLCG, in the next years.

8. Risks assessment

This report has presented the current costs for operating the NDGF-T1 using six HPC sites spread in four countries, a cost model for deploying the NDGF-T1 in a single site, and intermediate models, such as decreasing the number of HPC centers in the countries, or operating the current distributed NDGF-T1 with centralised personnel. This section evaluates the major risks that could be encountered in the transitions to the proposed alternatives.

Transition to a single-site

The transition to this model would take a few years: first by selecting the proper site that could host the complete NDGF-T1, then introducing new resources in the site as soon as other resources would be expiring, hiring/moving personnel to that HPC site, and establishing a competent 24x7 support for Tier-1 activities.

As seen in section 5 (Finding #5.4), this centralized model would offer a saving, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1, of ~ 0.7 M€/year. This is the typical in-kind contribution that is currently delivered to the distributed NDGF-T1. Even if the selected site to host the centralized NDGF-T1 could offer in-kind contributions to the project, they won't likely be as large as the current value. The reduction of personnel needs is estimated to -3.4 FTEs, as compared to the current NDGF-T1. But, as it has been explained in section 6, the competence should stay spread in the countries, for the benefit of local researchers and other projects. Taking into account 0.5 FTE for each of these sites, this would correspond to an additional personnel expense of ~ 300 k€/year, hence the final saving, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1, would be of ~ 0.4 M€/year.

In section 6, the deployment of the NDGF-T1 in a single-site is considered, with hardware tendered and purchased from each of the current sites that conform the NDGF-T1, but with the hardware finally deployed in a single-site placed in a Nordic country. This model would offer a saving, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1, of ~ 0.3 M€/year.

In this scenario, there is the risk that the spread knowledge reduces, and this would limit the LHC computing competences that have been settled in the Nordic countries. Also, sending money across borders to setup a single-site might be a challenge. Legal aspects to tender and purchase resources in a site and delivering resources in another country should be carefully considered.

Transition to a 1 HPC site per country

As seen in section 6, this configuration implies a reduction of HPC sites in Sweden and Norway. This would allow a reduction of costs, as compared to the current distributed NDGF-T1, of ~ 0.4 M€/year. This includes keeping some competences around, i.e. 0.5 FTE for sites that had previously offered resources to the Tier-1. The local support given to local users by local experts is an asset that shouldn't be lost.

The transition to this scenario brings low risks. As soon as resources would expire in one site, the new resources could be added/enabled in another site in the country. The reduction of HPC sites can be well aligned to national strategies for offering less, cost-effective, HPC sites for science. The countries affected are Sweden and Norway.

However, in this scenario with fewer sites per country, the distribution of resources for ALICE and ATLAS could become critical for service degradations in case of losing

one site. In this scenario, the single HPC site in Sweden would serve ~50% of the ATLAS resources for the NDGF-T1. Problems in this site would substantially degrade the NDGF-T1 towards ATLAS. Hence, a 24x7 support should be added in this particular site, to ensure commitment to the MoU requirements. This support would add additional ~50 k€/year in Sweden.

Since some of the HPC sites are very close to ALICE or ATLAS researchers, it might happen that 0.5 FTE for local support/connection to Tier-1 activities might not be seen as enough. This is another risk to contemplate in this scenario.

Transition to centralized operations

As seen in section 6 (Finding #6.2), this model does not offer a significant cost reduction, to even consider it as a viable option. It has many inherent risks as well, so it could affect the performance of the NDGF-T1, at least during the transition period.

9. Recommendations

This report provides suggestions for efficiency improvements that could be applied to the current NDGF-T1 distributed model, based on the performance results obtained by the NDGF-T1 in the last five years (Findings #3.1→#3.15).

The NDGF-T1 is operating as a Tier-1 for ~10 years. The number of HPC sites has been decreasing with time, with the goal of increasing efficiency and quality of service. The current configuration is conformed by six HPC sites spread in four countries. Reducing the number of sites and concentrating operational efforts and competences can achieve significant cost-savings and even better quality of services. However, the in-kind contributions and local expertise that are currently present in the current NDGF-T1 configuration will reduce if the number of sites reduces. This is of importance when evaluating the deployment of the NDGF-T1 in a single site.

There could be political (and even legal) difficulties in locating the entire NDGF-T1 at one location since it involves sending hard money (or material) across borders. The possible alternative for the NDGF-T1 with reduced number of sites in each country becomes interesting. This model has good resiliency built in, but it only offers a ~15% costs savings, as compared to the current Tier-1 deployment. Since WLCG contributions are seen as important and strategic, all of the countries would preserve all of their competences. This is one of main reasons at the Universities and sites for offering in-kind contributions to the Tier-1 activities. Considering that the NDGF-T1 might have already performed several optimisation steps during this ~10 years of operations, the effort and gain in this scenario should be carefully addressed, in view that the cost savings might not be very substantial.

As stated in section 8, there are many computing R&D activities towards the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC, by ~2025). In this scenario, the data volumes from the LHC detectors are expected to grow dramatically. Preliminary investigations show that the costs for deploying the needed resources will be at least a factor x5 away from flat-budget models, with the biggest impact in the deployed disk resources. The technology evolution alone will not help (as done up to date), and additional efforts to optimize the LHC computing are needed at all of the levels (software, resource utilization, hardware developments, ...). Most of the current activities focus in improving the LHC experiment computing models and operations, and in particular topics such as federating resources, storages, and elastically expand the resources to Cloud computing providers, will need the attention in the next years. The NDGF-T1 team is well positioned to collaborate to these activities. Both development and operations teams should consider the active involvement in many WLCG working groups that are being settled as of today, to address these topics.

It is worth mentioning that all of the Nordic research teams, universities, and or HPC sites have expressed their interest in continuing their participation in LHC Tier-1 computing activities, regardless the decision that is taken regarding the NDGF-T1 re-configuration in the future.

10. Conclusions

This report has addressed the performance of the current NDGF-T1, the running costs for the current NDGF-T1 distributed configuration, and estimation of the costs for running the NDGF-T1 in a single-site. Alternative models have been presented and their costs have been evaluated, such as reducing the number of HPC sites per country, or centralizing the current Operations efforts to the NeIC central Tier-1 team.

As expected, the cost of running the NDGF-T1 with resources spread in six HPC sites located in four countries (~ 3 M€/year) has some overheads as compared to the model of running the Tier-1 in a single site (~ 2.3 M€/year). These extra costs are related to additional personnel, network costs to interconnect all of the HPC sites, and redundant Tier-1 generic services. Even though, the current in-kind contributions from the sites (~ 0.7 M€/year) are equivalent to the savings that are seen when deploying the NDGF-T1 in a single-site. Also, there are many non-monetary aspects that are important to be considered. The Tier-1 activities are strategic for the sites and regions, as they positively impact in the quality of their LHC research activities, and they are beneficial to other science and technology fields (transfer of knowledge). Hence, some level of participation in the NDGF-T1 should be considered, even if the resources are deployed elsewhere. Worth saying that sending money across borders to fund this centralized NDGF-T1 model would be a real coordination challenge in the Nordic region.

This report shows that the current NDGF-T1 setup is well performing delivering computing resources to the ALICE and ATLAS collaborations, as compared to other WLCG Tier-1s. The alternative model that considers a reduction of sites to just one in each Nordic country is a good choice to be considered, since it minimizes the risks for degrading the current Tier-1 performance. However, this model would only offer $\sim 15\%$ savings as compared to the current NDGF-T1 configuration. Even if it would preserve the participation of all of the countries in the Tier-1 activities, without sending money across borders, the lose of local expertise for sites historically close to researchers, and the impact, should be carefully considered.

Last, but not least, the NDGF-T1 team can play important role in future R&D activities in WLCG, since many topics towards the HL-LHC are focused on storage federations, or complete site federations, as well as Cloud Computing resources exploitation. The NDGF-T1 is the only successful example of a Tier-1 exploiting resources from many HPC sites, hence their experience can be instrumental in some of these activities. Even if there are other Tier-1s that have eventually exploited HPC facilities in opportunistic mode, or Cloud Resources (even Amazon AWS is being integrated in Production in FNAL and BNL), the distributed storage and computing resources exploited by the NDGF-T1 team is unique, and it is seen with attention from the WLCG community. In particular, the expertise and ability to use time allocations in HPC sites can be very beneficial for sites considering the opportunistic exploitation of HPC resources, to elastically increase the level of resources, for some periods of time when it would be needed/asked by the LHC experiments.

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References

- [1] LHC: <http://home.cern/topics/large-hadron-collider>
- [2] CERN: <http://www.cern.ch>
- [3] WLCG: <http://wlcg.web.cern.ch>
- [4] WLCG MoU: <http://wlcg.web.cern.ch/collaboration/mou>
- [5] List to C-RRB agendas: <http://indico.cern.ch/categoryDisplay.py?categId=852>
- [6] REBUS: <https://wlcg-rebus.cern.ch/apps/pledges/resources>
- [7] HSo6 definition available at <https://hepux.caspar.it/benchmarks/doku.php>
- [8] LHCOPN: <http://lhcopn.web.cern.ch/lhcopn>
- [9] WLCG docs: <https://espace.cern.ch/WLCG-document-repository/default.aspx>
- [10] <http://stats.nordu.net/stat-q/load-map/ndgf,2016-05--08,traffic,peak>
- [11] <https://netstat.cern.ch/monitoring/network-statistics/ext/?p=LHCOPN>
- [12] SAM3 tests: <http://wlcg-sam.cern.ch>
- [13] XRootD protocol: <http://xrootd.org>
- [14] GGUS: <https://ggus.eu>
- [15] GOCDB: <https://gocdb.cern.ch/portal>
- [16] ALICE Monalisa monitoring: <http://alimonitor.cern.ch/map.jsp>
- [17] AliEn: <http://alien.web.cern.ch>
- [18] J.K. Nilsen, D. Cameron, A. Filipcic, ARC Control Tower: A flexible generic distributed job management framework, J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 664 062042, 2015
- [19] ATLAS HammerCloud: <http://hammercloud.cern.ch/hc/app/atlas>
- [20] Perfsonar-PS: <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/LHCOPN/PerfsonarPS>
- [21] OpenDCIM: <http://opendcim.org>
- [22] NeIC: <https://neic.nordforsk.org>
- [23] NBI: <http://www.nbi.ku.dk>
- [24] Danish Roadmap for Research Infrastructures document: <http://goo.gl/eOSCJo>
- [25] HIP: <https://www.hip.fi>
- [26] CSC: <https://research.csc.fi> - <https://goo.gl/ROkZmy>
- [27] *cPouta*: <https://research.csc.fi/cpouta>
- [28] UiB: <http://www.uib.no>
- [29] UiO: <http://www.uio.no>
- [30] Abel cluster: <http://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/hpc/abel>
- [31] *finn* cluster: <https://www.fimm.fi/en/services/technology-centre/it>
- [32] HPC2N: <https://www.hpc2n.umu.se>
- [33] NSC: <https://www.nsc.liu.se>
- [34] Abisko: <https://www.hpc2n.umu.se/resources/abisko>
- [35] Triolith: <https://www.nsc.liu.se/systems/triolith>
- [36] Amazon EC2: <https://aws.amazon.com>
- [37] MS Azure: <https://azure.microsoft.com>
- [38] Google Cloud: <https://cloud.google.com>
- [39] Sigma2: <https://www.sigma2.no>
- [40] PUE: <http://goo.gl/W7MQyK>
- [41] Eurostat: <http://goo.gl/t2AY4f>
- [42] LHCONE: <http://lhcone.web.cern.ch>
- [43] R. Gardner, et al, Data federation strategies for ATLAS using XRootD, J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 513 042049, 2014
- [44] EU e-fiscal: <http://efiscal.eu>
- [45] Bernd Panzer-Steindel, CTO CERN/IT, "Technology, Market and Cost Trends 2012", <https://goo.gl/pNsScL>
- [46] M. Alandes, M. Dimou, J. Flix, A. Forti, A. Sciabà, Optimising costs in WLCG Operations, J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 664 032025, 2015
- [47] "Computing Model Update", 2014
<http://cds.cern.ch/record/1695401/files/LCG-TDR-002.pdf>